

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Status of Asian elephant and Human-elephant conflict (HEC) in Asia: A brief and updated review

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Introduction

The Asian elephant (*Elephas maximus*), the only extant species of the genus *Elephas* which belongs to family Elephantidae of order Proboscidea is currently restricted to 13 countries in the Indian subcontinent and Southeast Asia (Sukumar, 2006). The range of Asian elephant does not extend beyond India to the west and Borneo to the east. However, this species once roamed an extended range from western Asia to the east as far as the Yangtze River in China (Olivier, 1978; Sukumar, 2006). The Asian elephant has disappeared from 95% of its historical range and currently distributed in discontinuous populations (Sukumar, 2006). The largest population of Asian elephants is found in the mainland of India (24,000-33,000) followed by considerable populations in Myanmar, Thailand, Sri Lanka, Malaysia and Indonesia (>1000). Small populations can be observed in Bhutan, Bangladesh, Cambodia, Lao PDR, Vietnam and China (<1000) (Sukumar, 2006). According to Menon and Tiwari (2019) the current total population of Asian elephants in the world is *c.* 48,323–51,680 in the wild and *c.* 15,000 in captivity which spreads over an area of 486,800 km². These figures give us a crude estimate of the population density of the species; ~0.10 individuals/km² or 10 individuals per 100 km². Given the body size of the Asian elephant, being the second largest terrestrial species of the world, this estimated density is considerably high and provides an indication how diminished and fragmented the populations are. Asia is also the most populated region of the world when human population is considered. Therefore, the obvious competition between the humans and elephants for the resources and habitats continues from the past to the present giving rise to the human-elephant conflict (HEC). With numerous threats mainly induced by habitat loss/fragmentation, poaching and HEC, the Asian elephant population has significantly declined by at least 50 percent over a period of less than 100 years (Sukumar, 1992). Therefore, *E. maximus* has been categorized as an endangered (EN) species (IUCN, 2021). This paper aims to briefly review the current status of Asian elephant and HEC in the present range of the species within different parts of Asia.

Keywords: *Elephas maximus*, elephant conservation, wildlife conflict, wildlife management, resource use

Human-elephant conflict (HEC)

A conflict occurs when two parties are incompatible over opposing interests and clash over a prolonged period. Therefore, HEC can be defined as the prolonged clash between the humans and elephants over the exploitation of land and resource use. HEC often involves crop-raiding by elephants and exploitation of natural habitats of elephants by the expansion of human settlements, developments and farmlands, which ultimately results in negative consequences. Mumby and Plotnik (2018) describes HEC as a variety of negative, physical interactions between humans and elephants. Perceptions and fear associated with this historical conflict extends beyond the direct interactions (Mumby and Plotnik, 2018) and more than often the two counterparties intrinsically fear over each other. The level of conflict differs spatially and temporally depending on a multitude of factors including resource distribution, agricultural practices, land use by humans, seasonal climatic conditions and habitat connectivity (Bal et al., 2011; Neupane et al., 2013; Cook et al., 2015; Goswami et al., 2015; Wilson et al., 2015; Mumby and Plotnik, 2018).

Figure 1: A herd of Asian elephants feeding on grass near a man-made reservoir in Sri Lanka

Status and severity of HEC in different parts of Asia

Based on the population densities of both humans and elephants, forest cover, agricultural area cover, past literature and reports available regarding the HEC, we categorized the level of conflict into three categories as: low, moderate and high. This categorization was based on the country wise distribution of Asian elephants and there may be localized regions where the severity level differs from the country wise assessment.

Table 1: Human and elephant population parameters of Asian elephant range countries by the year 2018 with estimated HEC level

Country Name	Total Land Area (km ²)	Forest Area (km ²)	Forest cover %	Agricultural area (km ²)	Agricultural area %	Human population (million)	Elephant population (average)	HEC level	Elephant Population trend
Bangladesh	130,170	18,834	14.5	92,023	70.7	161.4	363	High	Low
Bhutan	38,140	27,211.2	71.3	5,130	13.5	0.8	683	Low	Stable
China	9,424,702.9	2,162,190.4	22.9	5,285,287	56.1	1392.7	300	Low	Low
Indonesia	1,877,519	933,442.7	49.7	623,000	33.2	267.7	1,794	Moderate	Declining
India	2,973,190	716,272	24.1	1,796,740	60.4	1352.6	29,964	High	Stable
Cambodia	176,520	83,797.5	47.5	55,660	31.5	16.2	500	Moderate	Declining
Lao PDR	230,800	166,645	72.2	23,940	10.4	7.1	550	Low	Declining
Sri Lanka	61,864	21,193.4	34.3	28,116	45.4	21.7	5,879	High	Stable
Myanmar	652,790	291,233.1	44.6	128,890	19.7	53.7	3,000	Moderate	Low
Malaysia	328,550	192,143.4	58.5	85,710	26.1	31.5	3,490	Moderate	Declining
Nepal	143,350	59,620.3	41.6	41,210	28.7	28.1	127	Low	Low
Thailand	510,890	199,450	39.0	221,100	43.3	69.4	3,234	Low	Declining
Vietnam	310,070	144,912.9	46.7	121,688	39.2	95.5	114	Low	Declining

Data sources: Country wise land area data and human population data – Worldbank (2021); Elephant population data - Menon and Tiwari (2019)

According to Fernando and Pastorini (2011), the distribution of Asian elephant within its range is disproportionate where India and Sri Lanka alone harbors three fourth of the total population. Most of these countries can be considered highly agricultural and hence the level of conflict often increases elephant being a megaherbivore. Elephants often get attracted for cultivated crops/stored food products and humans exploit the forests for agricultural practices. Surprisingly, the elephant density within the island of Sri Lanka is extremely higher when total land area as well as forest cover are considered. In Sri Lanka, the distribution of elephant populations covers almost two third of the total area (Fernando et al., 2021) increasing the possibility of contact between the elephants and humans. This is facilitated by relatively low forest cover and high level of agriculture practiced (Table 1). Therefore, Sri Lanka can be identified as the country with highest level of HEC in Asia. Meanwhile in India, the elephant distribution is highly localized when the total land area is considered; major populations located in southern India and north-eastern India, with fewer in central India and north-west India (Menon and Tiwari, 2019). Therefore, despite the vast land area and forested areas available within the country, the remaining elephant populations have been trapped mostly in the hilly areas (Sukumar, 1992). This would result in higher elephant densities than the values generalized for countrywide figures as given in figure 1. A considerable HEC level can be observed within localized areas of India as a result of high human population pressure and diminishing forest cover which is at a very low level even now (Table 1). Menon and Tiwari (2019) recorded that the highest level of HEC prevails in Central India despite harboring 10% of the total elephant population of the country.

Bangladesh has the highest human population density of all 13 countries considered (Figure 2) with low level of forest cover (14.5%) and high agricultural area cover (70.7%). Despite the low number of elephants amounting less than 500, a considerable level of HEC can be observed in some regions of the country (Feeroz et al., 2004; Perera, 2009). The level of HEC varies with elephants migrating across the borders seasonally (Perera, 2009). In Indonesia, the elephant population is declining in the island of Sumatra mainly due to forest fragmentation and habitat loss. Despite the relatively high forest cover of the country, the forests occupied by elephants are limited in number and forest areas are shrinking. This has caused serious issues for the survival of the remaining elephant populations since most of the remaining forested landscapes are not large enough (<250 km²) to sustain elephants (Menon and Tiwari, 2019).

Forest destruction for oil-palm plantations has reduced the forest area and fragmented the distribution range of elephant populations in Malaysian Sabha (Othman et al., 2019). The movement of elephants has been restricted by the electric fences associated with the plantations (Menon and Tiwari, 2019). This can be identified as a serious issue in this region if escalates, which would greatly reduce the elephant population numbers. In Myanmar, Lao PDR and Cambodia, the main consideration regarding the conservation of elephants is the forest destruction and fragmentation. Capturing of wild elephants to maintain the captive populations in Myanmar may lead to the extinction of wild population of elephants within the country (Leimgruber et al., 2008). Myanmar currently has the largest captive elephant population in the world (Menon and Tiwari, 2019).

Figure 1: Density of Asian elephants within its range based on total area and forested land cover

Figure 2: Human population density by the year 2018 (Source: Worldbank, 2021)

In Thailand, the HEC is at a moderate level mainly due to the protection provided to the elephants by the high number of protected areas in the country and conservation and habitat restoration measures taken.

Bhutan can be considered an exception when the level of HEC is considered. While most of the other countries face high level of HEC, with a forest cover of 71.3 % and a lowest level of human population density (Table 1), Bhutan has able to sustain a considerable population of elephants in the southern region of the country bordering India. The low percentage of agricultural area further helps in reducing the conflict level.

The elephant populations in China, Nepal and Vietnam are extremely low and it's a matter of preventing the local extinction rather than addressing HEC in these countries.

Every year hundreds of people and elephants are killed as a result of HEC in addition to the number that gets injured. The damage caused by elephants to the agricultural crops and properties amount for millions of dollars. With the rate of human population growth, expansion of agricultural lands, habitat loss and habitat fragmentation keep increasing the level of conflict. The mortality rate of elephants by human involved causes and the rate of people being killed by elephants increase in an alarming rate specially in the South Asia mainly in Sri Lanka and India. Use of poison, electrocution and firearms has become a serious issue of conservation concern. Meanwhile, the heavy losses to humans including both financial and human lives, have created significant social and political complications. In most of the areas with high level of HEC, a large proportion of elephant habitat is outside the protected areas and is interspersed with agricultural land and human settlement (Menon and Tiwari, 2019) which complicates the situation that needs to be addressed. This situation can be clearly observed in the countries with high levels of HEC. Despite the large number of diverse mitigation measures that has been suggested and applied in many countries in Asia where HEC takes place, the scientists and managers have failed to find long term and sustainable solutions for the issue. There are certain scenarios where the mitigation measures have increased the level of tension between the humans and elephants. For example, the restriction of elephant migration by electric fencing and translocation of problem elephants have failed to reduce the HEC in some instances.

Therefore, while addressing the issue of HEC in short term by selecting the most suitable mitigation measures, identifying the broader issues that lie behind and finding sustainable solutions for the long term is highly recommended. In addressing this issue, better understanding of the social organization and ecology of elephants (Mumby and Plotnik, 2018), and trying to find a ecological balance between increasing human populations, expanding agricultural lands and elephant populations will be highly important.

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